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Methods and methods used during literacy training

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье рассказывается о правилах обучения грамоте учащихся начальных классов, методике и современных методах обучения грамоте.

Ключевые слова: Значение слова грамотность, алфавит, методика, звук, фонетика, языкознание, буквы виды звука.

Abstract: This scientific article talks about the rules of teaching literacy to elementary school students, the methodology and modern methods of teaching literacy.

Key words: The meaning of the word literacy, alphabet, methodology, sound, phonetics, linguistics, letters, types of sound.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga savod o'rgatish qoidalari, savod o'rgatishning metodikasi va zamonaviy usullari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: alifbe, metodika, tovush, fonetika, lingvistika, harflar, tovush turlari.

In order to properly organize literacy training, a special study of children's speech preparation is required. Previously, my child's special education began in

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August, and even earlier - in the spring. In this case, the family of the student entering the 1st grade was visited or the kindergarten, an interview was held, and the general knowledge level of the child was determined. Currently, children who are admitted to the 1st grade are specially prepared for teaching literacy. One-two, three-four-month training classes in some places have been organized for them. In the preparatory classes, children are introduced to letters and sounds, and elementary writing is also taught. Methodists are developing specific requirements and methodical recommendations for preparatory classes. Although the educational content and the period of organization of the preparatory classes are not the same, it is recommended to determine the following in order to study the speech preparation of my child during this period: 1. To determine the winter skill. a) reads the word by heart; b) reads in syllables; d) reads by letter (incorrect reading); e) knows a lot of letters, but does not know how to read; f) recognizes some letters. 2. Writing skills. a) knows how to write all letters, writes words (printed or written); b) knows how to write only some letters (printed or written); d) does not know how to write at all. 3. Readiness to analyze sound. a) divides the word into syllables; b) separates the sound in a word or syllable; d) pronounces all sounds correctly; e) pronounces some sounds incorrectly (which sounds are considered ckani); f) Attention is paid to the high or low speech, diction. 4. Verbal connected speech. Reciting the Shemi. a) knows 3 or more poems, recites them with pleasure; b) knows 1-2 poems, is shy to say them; d) he does not know how to recite any

2023

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poem by heart. 5. Verbal connected speech. Telling a story. a) knows and can tell one or more fairy tales; b) knows a fairy tale and tries to tell it, but cannot tell it; d) does not know how to tell a story, does not try to learn. 6. Verbal connected speech. Expression of opinion ("Tell me what you see in the picture"). a) A connected story of more than 20 words, can make several sentences; b) Can make several sentences from 10 to 20 words; d)) can answer up to 10 words in the form of connected speech; e) can give a short answer with 3-4 words.

Also, in this process, the syntactic structure of the child's speech and the range of words he uses are studied, the collected materials are written in two options: a) separate information about each student (this is necessary for an individual or differential approach to the child 'ladi); b) general information for students of the class (this name is used in the lesson to choose the methodology of general work for students of the class). It is known that students come to the 1st grade with different preparation. Educational materials are given consistently, according to the level of 1st graders. Nevertheless, students who come with different preparation will have different acquisitions. This requires a differentiated and individual approach to students in the process of teaching literacy. This approach gives good results at all stages of education. In the differential approach, students are divided into groups, each group is assigned tasks appropriate to their level and ability. Class students can be divided into 3 groups. Tasks are also developed in 3 options. The teacher conducts parallel work with students in 3

2023

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groups during frontal work in the classroom. For all 3 groups, the educational material is "Alifbe", in addition to it, handouts, tables, and independent work can be used. Pre-preparation of the educational material in the alphabet or the difficult part of the text being read is important to the careful student, then it is taught to a free student. It is necessary to work with some students individually outside of class. To know the culture of oral speech and its characteristics; teaching to structure sentences and speech in accordance with the norms of the literary language in terms of grammar, orthography, stylistics, developing oral speech and consistently increasing the student's vocabulary, acquiring practical knowledge of the syntactic structure of the sentence, speech units o to develop skills related to ensuring logical harmony between words, to achieve the reader's full understanding of the meaning of the words suggested by the new letter-sound, to create small interconnected stories based on the picture teach Carrying out educational activities related to the development of the student's connected speech.

1. Creating a story based on pictures;
2. Find a suitable title for the content of the picture;
3. "Alife" textbook and retelling of educational materials learned in extracurricular activities;
4. Answer the questions completely and accurately;
5. Paying attention to teaching the standards of literary speech in a practical way (in this field, the teacher's speech should be a model for the student);

2023

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6. Work on riddles, proverbs, wise words (based on textbooks and educational materials selected for reading outside the classroom);
7. When working with small groups, divide the students into intellectually equal groups, give problematic assignments to the groups to compose a connected text, and encourage the winning group based on the interpretation of the group's answer;
8. Encouraging the desire to develop one's own speech in one-on-one (individual) studies (on the basis of reading a dictionary, a new poem, a story, a fairy tale);
9. To read the words as a whole, to express the character of the character through tone;
10. Forming the ability to observe the punctuation marks used in text work;
11. Memorizing poems with 4 and 8 lines

Work on vocabulary. Enriching the student's speech, writing down words that are rarely used in their speech, paying attention to the use of words in the dictionary during the lesson. In the "Uzbekistan - My Country" department, children will be given the first understanding of our motherland, which gives all joy and happiness - Uzbekistan. The selected works ensure that the student understands the duty and responsibility towards the motherland. Cultivates the feeling of love for the country. We are the generation of greats. (11 hours) In the section "We are the generation of the greats", an understanding of our national values is provided by the examples of works dedicated to the lives of great scholars who have emerged from our nation. The reader will have an elementary idea of the

2023

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absence of the future without memory. Koklam - yashnaydiolam. (9 hours) In the "Koklam - yashnaydi olam" section, there are works that tell about the coming of the seasons, the unique features of the season of living, human life and the impact on the whole nature. Science is the light of the mind. (9 hours) Reading the works of art included in the section "Science - the light of the mind" will help the child to create an idea about the importance of books in human life, the influence of learning on mental thinking and the development of spiritual maturity. Education of the people is the key to happiness. (9 hours) "People - education is the key to happiness" event includes examples of oral creativity that entered the child's heart with mother's will, goodness, correct behavior, honesty, sophistication, friendship, comradeship, imagines about morality. decency is good for a person. The works included in the section "Etiquette - good for the human being" are intended to provide the first understanding of the main factors that determine the spiritual and moral image of a person, such as pride, modesty, decency, and contentment.

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